

ORIGINAL RESEARCH PAPER

Sports Science

STUDY ON COMPETITIVE ANXIETY OF CRICKET PLAYERS AT DIFFERENT AGE GROUPS

KEY WORDS: Competitive Anxiety, Age Group Of 14 Years And 16 Years Cricket Players.

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ABSTRACT

The present study investigated competitive anxiety among cricket players at different age groups. Objectives of the study: To compare the competitive anxiety between 14 years and 16 years age group cricket players. A sample comprised of 60 participants in competitive cricket matches at the club level 14 and 16 age group from district Budgam, J&K. Measuring the competitive anxiety level of cricket players. Moreover, measuring the competitive anxiety of the players through Sports Competitive Anxiety Test (SCAT) developed by Marten (1977) was used. To compare the competitive anxiety of cricket players of the 14 and 16 age group t-test was applied. The competitive anxiety for 14 years age group the mean and SD (15.40, 2.60) and 16 years age group the mean and SD (16.30, 3.90) respectively. It was revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of the 14 and 16 age group on variable competitive anxiety of cricket players of district Budgam, J&K.

INTRODUCTION

Sports are a social activity that exists from time immemorial. It brings people together as an individual, a group, a community a nation, and indeed as a world. There are various forms of sports that are played all around the world some requires only physical exertion, mental exertion or sometimes both some played individually and others as a team and some played for fun or recreation and others as a competition. Anxiety is a psychological condition that has an impact on the readiness of a person to perform a specific activity. It is a state that nearly every sports persons come across at some point of time in his career. It determines the goal that an athlete sets to be achieved and on which he works on day-to-day basis cricket being a team as well as competitive sport requires a lot of composure as well as great amount of motivation due to the nature of longer duration of play. College is a stressful time of challenges and transitions. College students are balancing many demands between classroom expectations, work, extracurricular activities, social life, and more (Thome & Espelage, 2004). The risk for mental health issues is increased for college students facing a great deal of stress (Kadison & DiGeronimo, 2004). Mental health is defined by the National Institute of Mental Health as the way one thinks, feels, and acts when coping with life and involves continued forward movement in abilities to perform daily physical tasks and challenges (National Institute of Mental Health, 2007). (American College Health Association, 2009) specified that depression and anxiety continue to be two of the most common health problems that university students experience, and are often experienced concurrently.

Objectives of the Study

To compare the competitive anxiety between 14 years and 16 years age group cricket players.

Hypothesis of the Study

There will be no significant difference in competitive anxiety between 14 years and 16 years age group cricket players.

Methodology

This study was comprised two groups that is 14 years age group and 16 years age group. The study was conducted on 60 cricket players from the different competitive cricket matches at the club level, district Budgam, Jammu and Kashmir. The samples were selected by using simple random sampling method. T-test was used to compare the competitive anxiety of 14 years and 16 years age group of cricket players in competitive cricket matches at the club level district Budgam, Jammu and Kashmir.

TOOLS

Sport Competition Anxiety test:

Items 1, 4, 7, 10, and 13 are filler items used to help disguise the purpose of the test; cross them out, as they will not be used for scoring. Items 2, 3, 5, 8, 9, 12, 14, and 15 are scored in the following manner: hardly ever=1 pt., sometimes=2 pts, often=3 pts. For items 6 and 11, the scoring is reversed: hardly ever=3 pts, sometimes=2 pts, often=1 pt. Simply total the numbers for these items to determine your trait anxiety score, which ranges from a low of 10, to a high of 30.

Ten of the items asses' individual differences in the extent of competition anxiety present in the athletes.

Analysis of Data

Statistical analysis was carried out by using SPSS and the result obtained is given below.

Objective. To compare the competitive anxiety between 14 years and 16 years age group cricket players.

Null Hypothesis. There will be no significant difference in competitive anxiety between 14 years and 16 years age group cricket players.

Table: Comparison Of Competitive Anxiety Between 14 Years And 16 Years Age Group Cricket Players

Variable	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Value	df	Sig.
Competitive Anxiety	14 years age group	30	15.40	2.60	-1.050	58	0.298
	16 years age group	30	16.30	3.90			

Not significant

Figure: Comparison Of Means & SD Of Competitive Anxiety Between 14 Years And 16 Years Age Group Cricket Players

The above table 1 indicates that the independent sample t-test is associated with a statistically non-significant difference $t(58) = -1.050, p = 0.298$ at the level of 0.05 significance. The result shows that 14 years age group cricket players ($M = 15.40, SD = 2.60$) and 16 years age group cricket players ($M = 16.30, SD = 3.90$) are found to have similar levels of anxiety. This suggests that there is no significant difference in the competitive anxiety levels between 14 years and 16 years age group cricket players of district Budgam, Jammu and Kashmir, as the p-value is greater than 0.05. So, the null hypothesis, "There will be no significant difference in competitive anxiety between 14 years and 16 years age group cricket players of district Budgam, Jammu and Kashmir" is accepted.

Findings of the Study

There is no significant difference in competitive anxiety levels between 14 years and 16 years age group cricket players of district Budgam, Jammu and Kashmir.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that the competitive anxiety levels between 14 years and 16 years age group among cricket players had shown no significant difference.

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